

Microscopic investigation on empirical force-field model dependent structure and dynamical properties of amino acids in aqueous medium[†]

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Aqueous amino acid solutions show several unusual properties by virtue of which they are widely used as additives to suppress protein unfolding and aggregation. In this work, we explore the structure and dynamical properties of the aqueous solutions of several osmolytic amino acids; valine, glycine, proline and phenylalanine by performing molecular dynamics simulations using two popular force fields; CHARMM and GROMOS with TIP3P and SPC/E water to explore the effects of these models in describing the properties of the amino acid solutions. We find that both CHARMM27 and GROMOS53A6 models can reproduce the experimental osmotic pressure in a more accurate manner than GROMOS43A1 model. We find that the restricted mobility as exerted by the amino acids involving all these models follow the similar trend. Moreover, the diffusion co-efficient values of the amino acids as obtained by using CHARMM and GROMOS force fields lie in a satisfactory regime. However, the cluster analysis infers that while all the amino acids mixed up with water homogeneously in their respective solutions involving CHARMM27 model, significant clustering occurs for proline involving GROMOS43A1 model. We find that while modeling with CHARMM27, the major probability exists for the formation of two membered cluster for all the amino acids used, with rare possibility of formation of 3–4 membered network, noticed for phenylalanine and valine. On the other hand, proline has noted to form microstructure of various sizes; as of 3–7 membered network while using GROMOS43A1 model. Interestingly, cluster forming probability get reduced with the use of GROMOS53A6 model. Formation of cluster network along with the differential restricted water-amino acid and amino acid-amino acid hydrogen bond dynamics as obtained by using different force field models proposes two diverge mechanisms, expected to be followed by the amino acid additives to stabilize the proteins.

Keywords: Amino acids, force field, simulation, diffusion, cluster.

1. Introduction

Amino acids, a building block of proteins are of great importance not only in understanding the biological processes, but also in industrial processes and day-to-day life. They are used as food additives, constituents of pharmaceutical products, preservatives for protein structures etc. It is well known that the three dimensional native folded form of proteins are sensitive to the environmental conditions. A relatively simple and efficient way to store protein solution is to use suitable excipients in the formulations. In modern era efficient preservation of protein structure constitutes an important area of research. Among several excipients, amino acids being a natural compound can be safely used as a class of solvent additive in industrial protein formulations to improve the sta-

bility of protein solutions. Among several amino acids, usages of arginine, proline, glycine, phenylalanine, valine etc. are quite popular^{1–5}. Experimental studies based on fluorescence spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering techniques have showed that arginine solution enhances protein refolding rate and prevent aggregation. However, there exists ambiguity in accepting arginine as protein stabilizer⁶. Spectrophotometric studies have shown that the stabilizing ability of an amino acid depends on the type of amino acid used¹. Apart from stabilizing capacity of the amino acid solution, such systems mimic the macromolecular crowding environment as normally seen in the intracellular environment⁷.

Aqueous amino acids have long been shown to possess unusual physical, colligative, and bulk properties such as

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anomalous viscosities and diffusion coefficients etc.⁸. By virtue of several unusual properties, amino acids are expected to change the vicinal water structure and dynamics, which in other way may affect the protein stability. Further, the amino acid themselves sometimes find to aggregate and enhance the protein stability. A recent quasi-elastic neutron scattering spectroscopic study on proline solutions of various concentrations infers that the reduction of water diffusion disrupts the self hydrogen bonding network of the water and hence make the aqueous proline solution more viscous⁹. Studies on the macromolecular crowding effects of highly crowded amino acid solutions have shown that the diffusion behavior of amino acids can differentiate between the effects of aggregation and obstruction^{10,12}.

Although amino acids are found to be a good preservative, the molecular level of understanding on their interactions with water to preserve protein's three dimensional structure is not properly known. Besides a volume of experimental studies, there exists a very few computational or theoretical studies on this topic. Therefore, to explore interactions of aqueous amino acid solutions with protein it is necessary to speculate the properties of bulk water-amino acid systems. In this context, it can be noted that choosing of force field models are essential for meaningful simulation studies to reproduce experimental behavior. In several recent studies, Elcock and co-workers have performed significant work on the highly crowded amino acid solutions using MD simulations with several force fields and have measured the density, viscosity, osmotic coefficients and dielectric properties of several amino acids^{10,11}. They have made thorough discussion on the similarities and discrepancies of the results obtained from their studies relative to the experimental evidences. However, their studies were silent about the structure and dynamical behaviors of the model dependent amino acid solutions which is essential to explain several biological functions of a system. Therefore, in this work, we have explored the properties of several amino acid solutions at various concentrations in a microscopic manner by performing molecular dynamics simulation studies. Attempts have been made to invent the effects of the popular force field models on the structure and dynamical properties of water as well as the amino acids in their respective solutions. Our such attempt would suggest the strength of each force field model used in this work.

In this study we have considered aqueous solutions of four different hydrophobic amino acids; valine, glycine, proline and phenylalanine since they are expected to act as an osmolyte, referral by several literature as mentioned earlier. The properties of the solutions were studied by using two popularly used force fields; CHARMM and GROMOS. Both the force fields are known to represent a statistical meaningful ensemble. The results obtained from these two different force fields are thoroughly compared. Finally, an attempt has been made to understand how could the properties of the amino acid solutions involving these two popular force-fields meet the criteria to act as a regulatory factor in protein stability. The rest of the article is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe in brief the setup of the systems and the simulation methods employed. The results are presented in detail and discussed in Section 3. The important findings and the conclusions reached from this study are summarized in Section 4.

2. System setup and simulation details

Sixty-four separate simulations with the glycine-water, phenylalanine-water, proline-water and valine-water at four different concentrations of 0.25 M, 0.5 M, 1 M and 2 M were carried out at ambient temperature with two different popular force fields say, CHARMM and GROMOS. The specific models used in this study are CHARMM27¹³, GROMOS43A1^{14,15} and GROMOS53A6¹⁶. TIP3P¹⁷ water model as compatible with the CHARMM force-field and SPC/E¹⁸ (extended simple point charge model) as compatible with the GROMOS force-field have been used for modeling of water. Additionally, CHARMM-SPC/E combination was used to perform simulations. Considering the fact that the force fields like CHARMM and GROMOS are developed with the three-site water models, TIP3P and SPC/E, respectively, we have not used any four-site water models in this work. However, recognizing the improvement of electrostatic distribution around the four-site water model, TIP4P, our future target has been to look into the properties of amino-acid solutions in this water and to provide a comparative details on the structure and dynamics of amino-acids in the water models of various sites. It may be noted that according to the amino acids used in this study, the 1 M and 2 M solutions are likely to be considered as crowded solutions (concentrations > 100 mg/ml). All the simulations were carried out using GROMACS code^{19,20}. The amino acids remain as zwitterions in the solution. The

concentrations used in this study are sometimes beyond the solubility of respective amino acids that may be considered in mimicking the cellular environment. The initial edge length of the cubic simulation cell was 40 Å. Initially, all the systems were minimized using conjugate gradient energy minimization method as implemented in the GROMACS code. The systems were then equilibrated for 5 ns at constant volume and temperature (NVT) followed by another 5 ns equilibration run under isothermal-isobaric ensemble (NPT) conditions at constant pressure of 1 atm. A production run of 70 ns duration was carried out for each system under NPT ensemble conditions. Hence the final trajectory length of each system becomes 80 ns. Further, to measure the diffusion co-efficient values an additional 10 ns trajectories were generated for each system using microcanonical (NVE) ensemble. The temperature and pressure of the systems were controlled by Nosé-Hoover thermostat and Parrinello-Rahman barostat^{21–23}. We employ periodic boundary conditions. The short range Lennard-Jones interactions were handled by using the grid system for neighbor searching. The cut-off distance for neighbor list was 1.4 nm. The long-range electrostatic interactions were calculated by using the particle-mesh Ewald sum (PME) method²⁴ with a grid spacing of 0.16 nm and an interpolation order of 4.

3. Results and discussion

In Fig. 1 we display the representative snapshots of the amino acid solutions at 1 M concentration as obtained at the

Fig. 1. Snapshots of the 1 M binary mixtures of (a) glycine-water, (b) phenylalanine-water, (c) proline-water and (d) valine-water as obtained at the end of the simulations performed by using CHARMM27+SPC/E (ii), CHARMM27+TIP3P (iii), GROMOS43A1+SPC/E (iv) and GROMOS53A6+SPC/E (v) models. The corresponding initial starting solutions are shown in the left panel (i).

end of the simulated trajectories involving CHARMM and GROMOS force fields. The initial snapshots of the starting solutions are also included in the figure for comparison. From the snapshots it can be noted that some amino acids in a particular force field model have a tendency to form clusters. This is an interesting observation. Governed by such behavior of the amino acids in their respective solutions, in this section we have analyzed the simulated trajectories in a microscopic manner. The results obtained from our calculations have compared with the available experimental data. We believe that our detailed analysis would shed light on the comparable osmolytic behavior of these amino acids at several concentrations and hence may guide us to choose the favorable force-field model required to fulfill the objective of the problem. The results presented in this section were obtained by analyzing the last 60 ns equilibrated trajectories of each system.

3.1. Structuration of water and amino acids in their respective solutions

The presence of amino acid in water is likely to modify the local structuring of the water molecules. Further, differential nature of the amino acids as well as their various concentrations may have heterogeneous effect on the structuration of water around them. The structuration of water and amino acids in their respective solutions has investigated by calculating the pair-correlation function, commonly known as radial distribution function, $g(r)$ between (i) water and oxygen atoms of the amino acid ($g_{OW}(r)$), (ii) water and nitrogen atoms of amino acid ($g_{NW}(r)$) and (iii) oxygen atoms of the water molecules ($g_{WW}(r)$). The calculations were carried out over the production trajectories of the amino acid solutions of several concentrations as generated by using CHARMM27, GROMOS43A1 and GROMOS53A6 force field models. The results as obtained by using CHARMM and GROMOS force fields are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. We find that all the curves consist of a sharp high intense first peak followed by two low intense broad peaks. Appearance of an intensified first peak is a signature of formation of water-amino acid hydrogen bonds. The details of hydrogen bonding properties will be discussed in the forthcoming section. The heterogeneous structuration of water around the polar oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the amino acids is evident from both the figures. It may be noted from Fig. 2 that the distribution pattern of TIP3P as well as SPC/E water

Fig. 2. Pairwise correlation function of water molecules as a function of distance from the (upper panel) oxygens of the amino acids ($g_{OW}(r)$), (middle panel) nitrogens of the amino acids ($g_{NW}(r)$), and (lower panel) oxygens of the water molecules ($g_{WW}(r)$) in several amino acid solutions of varying concentrations by using CHARMM27 force field model.

around the oxygen atoms of several amino acids is nearly similar. However, minimal increase in intensity of the distribution peaks is noticed as the concentration increases. Marginal higher water structure around the oxygen atoms in presence of proline as compared to the other amino acid is further evident from the figure. This is true irrespective of the concentrations used in this study. However, looking into the water structure around the nitrogen atoms of the amino acids, we find that the water around proline nitrogen behaves in a markedly differential way than around the nitrogen atoms of other amino acids. Water is noted to be more structured near the nitrogen atoms of phenylalanine, valine and glycine whereas it is significantly less structured near the nitrogen atoms of the proline. The distribution pattern of water around the polar atoms of the amino acids as obtained by using GROMOS force field is found to differ only for proline solution. It may be noted from Fig. 3 that irrespective of the concentration, water around the oxygen as well as nitrogen atoms of phenylalanine, valine and glycine is highly structured as compared to the nitrogens of proline. However, note the water structure around the oxygen and nitrogen atoms of proline involving GROMOS43A1 and GROMOS53A6 models. Water is found to be structured more around the proline oxygen involving GROMOS53A6 model whereas it remarkably reduces for GROMOS43A1 model. Again, it is interesting to note from the Fig. 3 that, around the nitrogen atoms of proline the water structure deteriorates significantly,

Fig. 3. Pairwise correlation function of water molecules as a function of distance from the (upper panel) oxygens of the amino acids ($g_{OW}(r)$), (middle panel) nitrogens of the amino acids ($g_{NW}(r)$), and (lower panel) oxygens of the water molecules ($g_{WW}(r)$) in several amino acid solutions of varying concentrations by using GROMOS43A1 and GROMOS53A6 force field models.

this is true irrespective of the GROMOS model involving 43A1 or 53A6 parameters. All such observations are found to be true, irrespective of the concentrations. This is an indirect indication of possibility of formation of lesser proline-water hydrogen bonds than the proline-proline hydrogen bonds. However, this needs to be investigated further. In addition to this, we find that the structuration of water among themselves are nearly similar in presence of amino acids up to 1 M solutions (see Figs. 2 and 3). However, little development of water structure at 2 M solution is evident from the $g_{WW}(r)$ curves, involving both the CHARMM and GROMOS models. Minimal increase in peak height for $g_{WW}(r)$ in phenylalanine solution is an indication of relatively higher self-structuration phenomenon of water at this solution as compared to the other amino acid solutions.

Driven by differential heterogeneous structuring pattern of the water molecules in presence of amino acids at several concentrated solutions, next, we have explored the structuration of amino acids. This was done by calculating the $g(r)$ between the center-of-masses of the amino acids ($g_{AA}(r)$) for all the systems. The results obtained from the equilibrated trajectories as generated by using CHARMM and GROMOS force field models are shown in Fig. 4. The results show several interesting phenomena. The broad peaks as observed from the $g_{AA}(r)$ curves for each amino acid at all

Fig. 4. Pairwise correlation function ($g_{AA}(r)$) between the center-of-masses of amino acid molecules as obtained from the several amino acid solutions of different concentrations by using CHARMM (upper panel) and GROMOS (lower panel) force fields.

concentrations involving CHARMM force field model is an indication of formation of closely packed layers of the corresponding amino acids, which may develop a cluster like network, more probable for glycine and valine. The tendency of formation of cluster network is noted to be more in presence of TIP3P water as compared to the SPC/E water. Surprisingly, the $g_{AA}(r)$ curves as obtained from the trajectories involving GROMOS force field show an opposite trend. Appearance of a significantly high intense peak in the $g_{AA}(r)$ curve for proline involving GROMOS43A1 model strongly suggests that proline molecules have an unusual tendency to aggregate among themselves. However, such possibility get reduced while using GROMOS53A6 model. It can be seen from the inset plots of Fig. 4 that except proline, all other amino acids exhibit comparable cluster forming probability involving GROMOS43A1 model whereas the use of GROMOS53A6 model enhances the cluster forming tendency of phenylalanine. We have noted that phenylalanine, among all exhibits highest cluster forming probability involving GROMOS53A6 model. Apparently, it seems from the figures that the cluster forming tendency of the amino acids depends on the concentration. An in-depth discussion on it can be found in the forthcoming section (Section 3.3). So far, our study in general suggests that the concentration of amino acid may play role in regulating the self-aggregation phenomena of the amino acids. This is an important observation and is expected to control the osmolytic behavior of several amino acids to protect protein's three dimensional native structures.

3.1.1. Radial distribution function and osmotic pressure:

Next, we have tried to investigate whether the radial distribution function of the amino acids can be correlated with the osmotic pressure of the amino acid solutions. This, in turn may provide information on the relative reliability of the force field models with the experimental observations. To do so, we have adapted a concept as proposed by Luo and Roux²⁵. According to their work, there exists linear relationship between the osmotic pressure and coordination number as can be obtained by integrating the $g(r)$ curves upto first minima. Further, Elcock and co-workers have shown the variation of osmotic coefficient values with increasing amino acid concentrations¹¹. Considering all these studies, it may be stated that there exists relationship between the coordination numbers (upto first minima of $g(r)$) and concentration of amino acids. Smith as well as Elcock and co-workers have shown that except for proline, the osmotic coefficients of the other amino acids used in this study remains nearly similar or decreases with increase in concentration^{11, 26}. Their studies have shown that the osmotic coefficients of proline remain nearly same up to certain concentration and after that it increases with increasing concentration. Considering all such reports, in our work we have calculated and plotted the coordination number up to the first minima of the amino acid-amino acid $g(r)$ curves at several concentrations. The nature of such plot has compared with the trend of osmotic coefficient vs concentration data as shown by Elcock and co-workers¹¹ as well as by the experimental reported trend²⁶. For this calculation, among several amino acid solutions we have considered proline-water and glycine-water systems, and have calculated $g(r)$ between the alpha-carbon atoms of these amino acids. The corresponding coordination number (CN) i.e. the average number of amino acid molecules that are present in close proximity to each other were also calculated by integrating the $g(r)$ curves. Fig. 5(a-d) represents both the quantities as a function of distance. In Fig. 5(e) and 5(f) we have plotted the CN values (N_{AA}) as a function of increasing concentrations of glycine and proline solutions. N_{AA} was obtained from the integration of $g(r)$ curves up to the first minimum of 6.5 Å. The figures showed that N_{AA} remains almost similar with increase in concentration for glycine involving GROMOS model whereas with the involvement of CHARMM model it mostly decreases. Further, the N_{AA} for proline remains nearly similar or increases slightly with the

Fig. 5. Pairwise correlation function ($g(r)$) between the alpha-carbon atoms of amino acid molecules (a and b) and the coordination numbers (CN) as a function of distance (c and d) obtained from the glycine and proline solutions of different concentrations by using CHARMM and GROMOS force fields. N_{AA} values as a function of concentrations have shown in (e) and (f).

concentrations involving CHARMM as well as GROMOS53A6 models. Such trends are in agreement with the experimental and other computational studies as mentioned above^{11,26}. Additionally, note the significant decrease in N_{AA} values for proline with increase in concentration involving GROMOS43A1 model. Our results infer that CHARMM27 and GROMOS53A6 models can reproduce the experimental osmotic pressure in a more accurate manner than GROMOS43A1 model.

3.2. Translational mobility of water and amino acids

To understand the differential local structuring of water as well as amino acids involving two different empirical force fields, we have calculated the translational mobility of the water molecules and the amino acids present in the solutions. The translational mobility of the solvents can be described by measuring diffusion coefficients of the solvents. The diffusion can be determined as self diffusion or as mutual diffusion. The former describes the translational mobility of individual molecules in the solution whereas the later provides collective information. Since we are interested in molecular mobility, the self diffusion coefficients for water and amino acids were measured from the mean-square displacements (MSD), defined as $\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle$,

$$\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle = \langle |r_i(t) - r_i(0)|^2 \rangle \quad (1)$$

where $r_i(t)$ and $r_i(0)$ are the position vectors of the oxygen atom of the i -th water molecule and that of center-of-mass of the amino acids at time t and at $t = 0$ respectively, and the averaging is carried out over different time origins with the tagged water and amino acid molecules separately. The calculations are carried out using 10 ns trajectory generated under NVE condition. In Figs. 6 and 7 we have displayed the translational mobilities of the water and the amino acids respectively. It can be seen from both the figures that, with increase in concentration the translational mobilities of water

Fig. 6. Mean square displacements (MSD), $\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle$, of water molecules present in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations using CHARMM (left panel) and GROMOS (right panel) force fields.

as well as amino acid molecules get restricted due to the formation of crowded environment. This is true irrespective of the force field models used in this study. The restricted heterogeneous mobilities of water in different amino acid solutions become prominent at higher concentration (Fig. 6). We find that irrespective of the force field and the water model used, the general trend of increasing restricted mobility of water follows the order: glycine < proline < valine < phenylalanine. As mentioned, the trend becomes prominent at 1 M and 2 M solutions. This is in accordance with the trend of structuration of the water around these amino acids. Looking at the results obtained from the trajectories involving

CHARMM27 force-field using TIP3P and SPC/E water, we find that SPC/E water diffuses slowly than the TIP3P water. This is in agreement with several previous findings on these two water models^{27,28}. Presence of different amino acids in solutions is not found to have any marked influence on the water mobilities involving GROMOS43A1 or 53A6, except for the mobilities of water in proline solutions at higher concentrations. Looking to the translational mobilities of the amino acid molecules (Fig. 7), we find that the increase in restricted translational mobility of the amino acids mostly follows the order: proline < glycine < valine < phenylalanine involving CHARMM27 model. As previous, in presence of SPC/E water, the mobilities of amino acids have noted to be restricted. Surprisingly, the mobilities of amino acids involving GROMOS43A1 model, found to follow the order: glycine < valine < phenylalanine < proline. Importantly, GROMOS53A6 derived amino acid mobilities are found to follow the trend similar to CHARMM27 derived mobilities, with the interchange in the position of glycine and proline. The extreme slow translational motions of proline involving GROMOS43A1 model might be the results of their self aggregating phenomena, that restrict the proline molecules to diffuse away. In this context, it may be noted that proline has been cited to be a good preserving agent for proteins. Thus the contradictory behavior of proline involving CHARMM27

and GROMOS53A6 against GROMOS43A1 model suggests two plausible mechanisms for the proline to act as a good osmolyte; either by its self-aggregation property (in case of GROMOS43A1) or by its fast diffusive nature (in case of CHARMM27 and GROMOS53A6). For the protein in proline solution, both such properties may reduce the possibility of formation of protein-proline hydrogen bonds, which in other hand may facilitate to preserve the intra protein hydrogen bonding network necessary to maintain protein's three dimensional native folded conformation. However, such explanation requires further in-depth study of a protein in proline solution. We are working on such aspects in our laboratory.

The differential mobilities of water and amino acids in the solutions are also evident from the calculated diffusion coefficient values of the water and amino acid molecules. The diffusion coefficient values were obtained from the slopes of the corresponding MSD ($\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle$) curves by using the well-known Einstein's equation²⁹,

$$D_E = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle}{2d\Delta t} \quad (2)$$

where d is the dimensionality of the system. The estimated self-diffusion coefficient values as obtained from the CHARMM and GROMOS force fields using different water models are listed in Tables 1–4. The experimental diffusion

Fig. 7. Mean square displacements (MSD), $\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle$, of amino acid molecules present in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations using CHARMM (left panel) and GROMOS (right panel) force fields.

Table 1. Self diffusion coefficients of water (D_w ($10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)) as obtained from several amino acid solutions of different concentrations by using CHARMM27 force field

System	TIP3P (M)				SPC/E (M)			
	0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
Gly	4.67	2.14	3.92	3.50	2.24	2.17	1.91	1.72
Phe	4.41	4.00	3.39	2.15	2.18	1.94	1.59	0.91
Pro	4.63	4.32	3.69	3.01	2.26	2.02	1.86	1.28
Val	4.41	4.00	3.62	2.59	2.17	1.99	1.72	1.13

Table 2. Self diffusion coefficients of water (D_w ($10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)) as obtained from several amino acid solutions of different concentrations by using GROMOS force field

System	43A1 and SPC/E (M)				53A6 and SPC/E (M)			
	0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
Gly	2.41	2.30	2.17	1.97	2.29	2.24	2.21	1.91
Phe	2.25	2.16	1.71	1.29	2.16	2.04	1.73	1.19
Pro	2.21	2.23	1.96	1.46	2.19	2.15	1.88	1.45
Val	2.15	2.09	1.84	1.40	2.12	2.12	1.74	1.37

Table 3. Self diffusion coefficients of amino acids (D_{AA} (10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹)) as obtained from several amino acid solutions at different concentrations by using CHARMM27 force field

System	TIP3P (M)				SPC/E (M)			
	0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
Gly	0.57	0.76	0.56	0.37	1.15	0.52	0.54	0.30
Phe	0.56	0.58	0.34	0.14	0.31	0.31	0.12	0.04
Pro	0.87	1.13	0.68	0.57	0.70	0.58	0.56	0.37
Val	0.97	0.42	0.40	0.39	0.87	0.50	0.30	0.17

Table 4. Self diffusion coefficients of amino acids (D_{AA} (10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹)) as obtained from several amino acid solutions at different concentrations by using GROMOS force field

System	43A1 and SPC/E (M)				53A6 and SPC/E (M)			
	0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
Gly	0.90	0.54	0.88	0.68	1.42	1.30	0.79	0.72
Phe	0.46	0.39	0.17	0.13	0.50	0.51	0.32	0.17
Pro	0.33	0.21	0.09	0.02	0.52	0.66	0.58	0.39
Val	0.45	0.62	0.42	0.43	0.45	0.84	0.49	0.30

coefficient for bulk liquid water is 2.3×10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹^{30,31} and it is therefore worth noting that the diffusion coefficient values that we report here for water in presence of several amino acids are relevant and can be proved by experimental setup. Further, it may be noted that the diffusion coefficient values as we report here for the amino acids, phenylalanine, valine, and proline by using CHARMM force field whereas that for valine and glycine by using GROMOS force field at several concentrations reproduce well the experimental data^{12,32,33}.

3.3. Clustering properties of amino acid molecules

Our studies, so far have shown that there exists a possibility of formation of microstructure for some amino acids at several concentrations. In order to explore this in a more precise manner, in this section we have calculated the probability of micro-aggregate formation of the amino acids at different concentrations. The amino acids are considered to form a cluster network when any of the polar atoms of the amino acids fall within the hydrogen bonding distance of 3.5 Å. Hence the polar atoms act as a building block of such clustering network. By this we are able to trap the clusters of several size over the equilibrated trajectories for each system. In Fig. 8 we have shown the probability distribution of the average cluster size that formed over the equilibrated trajectories of different amino acid solutions involving CHARMM and GROMOS models. Mostly two membered clusters are found to form in a greater extent involving

Fig. 8. Distribution of average cluster size for several amino acid solutions at different concentrations as obtained from the equilibrated trajectories generated by CHARMM (left panel) and GROMOS (right panel) force fields.

CHARMM27, irrespective of the water models used in this study. The cluster forming tendency is further noted to be increased with concentrations. In addition to this, the probability of formation of higher membered network is noted to be less for CHARMM-SPC/E whereas it increases with the addition of more amino acids involving CHARMM-TIP3P model. Formation of such relatively expanded network by the amino acids in concentrated solutions is particularly seen for all the amino acids except proline while using TIP3P model and for valine while using SPC/E water. Proline molecules are noted to involve exclusively in the formation of two membered network. All such observations are in agreement with the distribution pattern of the amino acids around themselves, as discussed in the previous section. Formation of two membered network is an indirect evidence of formation of possible direct amino acid-amino acid hydrogen bonds in the solutions. We will discuss this again in the forthcoming section. In contrast to the results obtained from the CHARMM27 force field, the results obtained from the GROMOS43A1 model are surprisingly different, as previously noted. The probability of formation of cluster of any size is significantly smaller for all the amino acids except proline. However, the tendency to form cluster increases with the addition of more amino acids. It may be observed that proline forms 3–4 mem-

bered network in a significant amount, with the probability of forming bigger size clusters (> 5), particularly at higher concentration. In Fig. 9 we have shown a representative snapshot of a microstructure formed by seven proline molecules as trapped from the 1 M solution by involving GROMOS43A1 force field. Also we have displayed a small three membered network of phenylalanine molecules as obtained from the

Fig. 9. Representative snapshot of a 7 membered cluster formed by the proline molecules and a 3 membered cluster formed by the phenylalanine molecules in the proline-water and phenylalanine-water solutions of 1 M concentration as obtained by using GROMOS43A1 and CHARMM27 force field respectively.

trajectory generated using CHARMM force field at the similar concentration. Again, in contrast to the GROMOS43A1 model, we find that there is a least tendency of proline GROMOS53A6 model to form bigger-network. Similar to GROMOS43A1 model, at lower concentration all the amino acids involving GROMOS53A6 model are also found to form 2 membered network at lesser probability, however, as the concentration increases such probability is noted to be increased, particularly for the proline. Our such findings correlate well with the studies on amino acid solutions as done by Elcock and co-workers^{10,34} where they have shown that the unphysical aggregation of proline as arises with the use of GROMOS43A1 model might have occurred from the van der Waals parameters which have been rectified in the GROMOS53A6 model³⁴.

3.4. Hydrogen bond dynamics

In an effort to find out the origin of differential structure and diffusive behavior of water as well as amino acids in their respective solutions at different force fields, we have tried to explain the origin of the heterogeneous behavior of the amino acids and water in their respective solutions by

observing the dynamics of amino acid-water (AW) hydrogen bonds that formed between amino acids and water molecules as well as amino acid-amino acid (AA) hydrogen bonds that formed between two amino acid molecules. The definition of hydrogen bonds is based on a purely geometric criteria³⁵⁻³⁷. According to this criteria, the distance between the tagged donor and the acceptor heavy atoms must be within 3.5 Å, and the angle between the hydrogen atom, the donor heavy atom and the acceptor heavy atom must be less than 30°.

The calculation of dynamics of hydrogen bonds is based on a time correlation functions (TCFs), namely, the intermittent hydrogen bond TCF, $C(t)$, defined as^{38,39},

$$C(t) = \frac{\langle h(0)h(t) \rangle}{\langle h(0)h(0) \rangle} \quad (3)$$

The function is based on hydrogen bond population variable $h(t)$ which is unity when a particular pair of sites (AW and AA) are hydrogen bonded at time t according to the definition used, and zero otherwise. The angular brackets denote that the results for a particular type of hydrogen bonds are obtained by averaging over all the hydrogen bonds of that type formed at different reference initial times. According to the definitions, $C(t)$ describes the probability that a particular hydrogen bond formed at time $t = 0$ is intact at a later time t . $C(t)$ is therefore independent of possible breaking and reformation of hydrogen bonds at intermediate times and hence the long-time diffusive behavior are included in $C(t)$. Therefore, by monitoring $C(t)$ one can obtain information about the time scale of overall structural relaxation of a particular type of hydrogen bond.

In Figs. 10 and 11 we have shown the hydrogen bond TCFs; $C_{AW}(t)$, formed between the amino acid and water; $C_{AA}(t)$, formed between the amino acids; and $C_{WM}(t)$, formed between the water molecules in their respective solutions. As previous, the results were generated from the equilibrated trajectories involving CHARMM (Fig. 10) and GROMOS (Fig. 11) force field models. It is clear from the figures that the structural relaxations of the AW and AA hydrogen bonds for different amino acid solutions are heterogeneous in nature. We find that the structural relaxations of hydrogen bond TCFs of AW and AA hydrogen bonds for the different amino acid solutions are in excellent agreement with their diffusive behavior as well as with the cluster-forming probabilities at the respective force field and water model. The restricted relax-

Fig. 10. Intermittent hydrogen bond time correlation functions, $C_{AW}(t)$, for the AW hydrogen bonds formed by water molecules and the polar atoms of the amino acid, $C_{AA}(t)$, for the AA hydrogen bonds formed by polar atoms of amino acid molecules, and $C_{WW}(t)$, for the WW hydrogen bonds formed by the water molecules in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations as obtained by using CHARMM27 force field.

ations of the intermittent TCFs for both AW and AA hydrogen bonds as obtained by using CHARMM27 model (see Fig. 10) generally follows the order: proline < glycine < valine < phenylalanine, (glycine \approx proline for AW hydrogen bonds). Such ordering is noted to be true irrespective of the water models used in the study. The AW hydrogen bond dynamics involving SPC/E and TIP3P water show almost similar result, however marginal restricted structural relaxation of hydrogen bonds involving SPC/E water as compared to TIP3P model is noticed. This is quite consistent with several earlier studies^{27,28}. The dynamics of AA hydrogen bonds in presence of either TIP3P or SPC/E water in the solution show comparable results. The formation of cluster-network among the amino acids is expected to play role in controlling the AA hydrogen bond dynamics. It may be noted from Figs. 10 and 8 that increase in probable cluster forming tendency hinders the respective amino acid molecules to diffuse away. This could be one of the important factors responsible for the slower structural relaxation of the hydrogen bonds that formed between the corresponding amino acids. Looking at the Fig. 11, we find that the restricted slow structural relaxations of AW and AA hydrogen bonds involving GROMOS43A1 model follows the order: glycine < valine < phenylalanine < proline, whereas, the trend is noted to follow the order: glycine < proline < valine < phenylalanine while using GROMOS53A6 model. Considering the nearly comparable structural relax-

Fig. 11. Intermittent hydrogen bond time correlation functions, $C_{AW}(t)$, for the AW hydrogen bonds formed by water molecules and the polar atoms of the amino acid, $C_{AA}(t)$, for the AA hydrogen bonds formed by polar atoms of amino acid molecules, and $C_{WW}(t)$, for the WW hydrogen bonds formed by the water molecules in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations as obtained by using GROMOS force field.

ation pattern of hydrogen bonds involving glycine and proline in their respective solutions, the trend is noted to be nearly similar to that obtained from the CHARMM27 model. The relaxations of phenylalanine-phenylalanine hydrogen bonds involving CHARMM27, and proline-proline hydrogen bonds involving GROMOS43A1 force field, are noted to be the slowest as compared to the hydrogen bonds formed between the other amino acids involving these force field models. The $C_{AW}(t)$ function involving these two amino acids in the respective force field models decays very slowly, attains a plateau value and remains constant. This is particularly true for the proline-proline hydrogen bond dynamics at all the concentration involving GROMOS43A1 model. However, the relaxations of the function $C_{WW}(t)$ for the WW hydrogen bonds formed by different water molecules show nearly similar relaxation behavior irrespective to the concentrations, and the force field used. Slightly heterogeneous relaxation pattern of the WW hydrogen bonds for different solutions are observed as we increase the concentration. The slowest relaxation of the $C_{AW}(t)$, $C_{AA}(t)$, and $C_{WW}(t)$ functions of several hydrogen bonded pairs of the phenylalanine-water systems involving CHARMM force field and those for proline-water systems involving GROMOS43A1 force field as compared to the corresponding functions of other systems once again infers that the cluster forming probability in these two systems is relatively more than in the other solutions. This correlates well

with the results obtained from the cluster analysis, as discussed earlier. The snapshot as shown in Fig. 9 on the self-assembled hydrogen bonded phenylalanine and proline molecules is an evident of such phenomena. We have fitted all the decay curves with multiexponentials and calculated the amplitude-weighted average relaxation times, $\langle\tau_C^{AW}\rangle$, $\langle\tau_C^{AA}\rangle$ and $\langle\tau_C^{WW}\rangle$, which are listed in Tables 5–8. The average relaxation times of the different types of hydrogen bonds once again reflects the trend of relaxation of the $C(t)$ functions, as discussed in this section. The magnitude of aver-

age relaxation times for AW and WW hydrogen bonds are in a comparable range for both the force fields used. However, we find that the relaxation times as obtained from the two different force field for the AA hydrogen bonds are significantly different in magnitude. The AA hydrogen bonds involving CHARMM27 force field are noted to take significantly longer time for relaxation as compared to the other models. However, exception of this can be found in the relaxation behavior of proline-proline hydrogen bonds involving GROMOS43A1 model. Further, note that except this, the

Table 5. Average relaxation times $\langle\tau_C^{AW}\rangle$, and $\langle\tau_C^{AA}\rangle$ as obtained from intermittent hydrogen bonds TCFs for amino acid-water and amino acid-amino acid hydrogen bonds formed in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations by using CHARMM27 force field

Model	System	$\tau_{AW}(\text{ps}) (M)$				$\tau_{AA}(\text{ps}) (M)$			
		0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
TIP3P	Gly	10.82	16.91	11.50	17.30	128.50	150.23	176.44	299.62
	Pha	15.50	16.90	31.79	42.64	323.10	282.60	729.10	767.10
	Pro	10.31	10.78	12.60	13.62	56.79	66.36	60.25	88.02
	Val	10.97	14.24	19.55	10.69	279.41	48.91	336.59	440.64
SPC/E	Gly	23.30	16.78	18.68	23.64	138.79	126.60	203.69	209.74
	Pha	34.05	25.05	35.35	68.12	486.60	337.02	378.96	396.66
	Pro	21.25	17.40	19.89	26.65	74.94	59.62	87.95	104.42
	Val	25.79	17.64	29.75	57.49	298.49	246.96	343.49	353.80

Table 6. Average relaxation times $\langle\tau_C^{AW}\rangle$, and $\langle\tau_C^{AA}\rangle$ as obtained from intermittent hydrogen bonds TCFs for amino acid-water, and amino acid-amino acid hydrogen bonds formed in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations by using GROMOS force field

Model	System	$\tau_{AW}(\text{ps}) (M)$				$\tau_{AA}(\text{ps}) (M)$			
		0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
43A1	Gly	7.30	8.52	9.35	10.17	3.23	10.16	3.79	3.99
	Pha	12.54	14.12	17.19	25.78	24.05	21.04	26.34	61.98
	Pro	37.70	22.67	34.60	81.43	350.95	336.13	229.35	378.45
	Val	11.09	12.51	13.95	18.08	5.20	11.85	11.74	16.11
53A6	Gly	8.05	7.84	8.19	9.00	3.77	3.44	3.55	4.11
	Pha	12.27	12.70	15.68	23.75	38.75	19.92	36.58	57.17
	Pro	9.25	9.43	10.49	13.75	5.69	7.28	8.01	31.32
	Val	11.00	11.71	13.09	16.64	7.59	11.62	12.64	11.34

Table 7. Average relaxation times $\langle\tau_C^{WW}\rangle$ as obtained from intermittent hydrogen bonds TCFs for water-water hydrogen bonds formed in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations by using CHARMM27 force field

Systems	CHARMM + TIP3P (M)				CHARMM + SPC/E (M)			
	0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
Gly	3.38	7.56	3.61	4.13	7.64	7.42	8.05	8.51
Pha	3.66	3.73	4.39	6.67	8.19	8.55	10.36	16.91
Pro	3.54	3.56	4.01	5.37	7.78	8.01	25.13	12.75
Val	3.55	3.62	4.12	5.66	7.86	8.23	9.67	13.92

Table 8. Average relaxation times $\langle\tau_C^{WW}\rangle$ as obtained from intermittent hydrogen bonds TCFs for water-water hydrogen bonds formed in several amino acid solutions of different concentrations by using GROMOS force field

Systems	43A1 + SPC/E (M)				53A6 + SPC/E (M)			
	0.25	0.5	1	2	0.25	0.5	1	2
Gly	7.41	7.34	7.55	8.09	7.42	7.24	7.47	8.01
Pha	7.82	8.13	9.29	12.54	7.84	8.00	7.48	12.35
Pro	7.79	7.90	8.56	10.45	7.79	7.73	9.24	10.86
Val	7.72	7.92	8.83	11.37	7.78	7.81	8.78	11.34

amplitude weighted average relaxation times for AA hydrogen bonds involving several amino acids are in a comparable range among themselves within the same force field model.

4. Conclusion

In this work we have studied the structure and dynamical properties of osmolytic amino acid solutions namely, glycine-water, valine-water, proline-water and phenylalanine-water at four different concentrations; 0.25 M, 0.5 M, 1 M and 2 M by using popular empirical force field models; CHARMM27 and GROMOS43A1, GROMOS53A6 with TIP3P and SPC/E water. The results obtained from our study involving several force field models have been thoroughly compared among them. Finally, efforts have been made to understand how could the dynamical properties of the amino acid solutions involving these two popular force-fields meet the criteria to act as a regulatory factor in protein stability.

The structuration of water around the oxygen atoms of the amino acids is found to be nearly similar for all the amino acid used in this study irrespective of the water model used, only marginal high structuration of water around oxygen in presence of proline has been noticed. However, interestingly, water around proline nitrogen noted to behave in a markedly differential way than around the nitrogen atoms of other amino acids. We find that water is least structured around nitrogen atoms of proline as compared to the other amino acids. Looking at the water distribution around the oxygen or nitrogen atoms of the amino acids involving different force field models, we find that among all, structuration of water is highest around the oxygen of proline involving CHARMM27 whereas it is lowest involving GROMOS43A1. Further, the distribution of the amino acids around themselves in general indicates the presence of closely packed layer of the respective amino acids, indicating a possible formation of cluster network. This is noted to be more when we use TIP3P as compared to the SPC/E water. The packing is noted to be more for glycine and valine as compared to the other two amino acids involving CHARMM27 whereas involvement of GROMOS43A1 model suggests the existence of significantly dense proline layer around themselves as compared to the other amino acids, suggesting the formation of proline microstructure of several sizes. However, such possibility is found to be less for GROMOS53A6 model. We find that there

exists relationship between the coordination numbers (upto first minima of $g(r)$) and concentration of amino acid which can be directly correlated with the trend of variation of osmotic coefficient with concentration. Our findings infer that CHARMM27 and GROMOS53A6 models can reproduce the experimental osmotic pressure in a more accurate manner than GROMOS43A1 model.

We further report that irrespective of the force field used in this study, the restricted mobility of water follows the order: glycine < proline < valine < phenylalanine, particularly at higher concentration. This is in accordance with the trend of structuring pattern of the water around themselves in presence of these amino acids. However, it is surprise to note that while the restriction in translational mobility of the amino acid follows the order: proline < glycine < valine < phenylalanine for CHARMM27 model, the trend is glycine < valine < phenylalanine < proline for GROMOS43A1. Further use of GROMOS53A6 gives the similar trend as obtained by using CHARMM27. This indicates that the restricted heterogeneous mobility of the glycine, valine and phenylalanine follow similar trend for any of the force field model however the model dependent heterogeneous behavior is noticed only for proline. We find that the diffusion coefficient values of the phenylalanine, valine, and proline as obtained by using CHARMM force-field and that obtained for valine and glycine by using GROMOS matches well with the reported experimental data at several concentrations, indicating the reliability of both the force fields.

Our additional analysis on cluster network shows that there exists significant possibility of formation of two-membered cluster while using CHARMM27 force field for all the amino acids with some possibility of forming higher membered network for valine at 2 M solution and lowest probability for proline at all concentrations compared to others. However, the heterogeneous structuring pattern of the amino acids around themselves infers that the formation of microstructure is highest for proline while GROMOS43A1 model was used. Proline in GROMOS43A1 is noticed to form significant amount of 3–4 membered cluster, with some possibility of formation of relatively bigger cluster of more than 4 membered quite efficiently at all the concentrations. The possible formation of cluster network is noticed to be enhanced the amino acid-amino acid hydrogen bonding ability. For GROMOS53A6 model, we find that there exists possible for-

mation of 2 membered cluster, as like CHARMM27 model, however propensity of this is noted to become more for proline at higher concentrations. Such unphysical aggregation of proline for GROMOS43A1 model might have occurred from the van der Waals parameters of nitrogen atoms of proline which have been rectified in the GROMOS53A6 model³⁴. We find that the restricted hydrogen bond dynamics for AW and AA hydrogen bonds formed between water and amino acid as well as between the amino acids themselves mostly follows the trend proline < glycine < valine < phenylalanine involving CHARMM27 model, whereas that obtained by using GROMOS43A1 and GROMOS53A6 model is noticed to be glycine < valine < phenylalanine < proline, and glycine < proline < valine < phenylalanine, i.e. the slowest relaxations of AA hydrogen bond dynamics have been observed for phenylalanine and proline involving CHARMM27, GROMOS53A6 and GROMOS43A1 force field respectively. It is significant to note that if we remove proline from the comparison list, the restricted hydrogen bond relaxation dynamics as exhibited by the other amino acids become exactly similar for all the force field models used in this study. Hence according to the force field models used proline can be marked out easily due to its unusual behavior.

Our analysis on the structure and dynamical properties of amino acid solutions of several concentrations, using different force fields models, suggests that the formation of inter amino acid and water-amino acid hydrogen bonds as well as the packing of mixed solvation layer probably would play vital role in preserving protein structure. The force field model dependent differential trend of restricted mobilities, cluster forming abilities as well as restricted hydrogen bond dynamics of several amino acid solutions in somewhat further demonstrate that there may exist two different plausible mechanisms of prevention. One possibility is through the formation of additive microstructure and the restricted relaxations of hydrogen bond dynamics, which may prevent the additives to form hydrogen bonds with the protein and hence may resist to break protein's intra-hydrogen bonding network, thereby can assist the protein to retain its folded form. Other possibility could be the faster relaxation of protein-additive hydrogen bonds, which may allow the amino acid additives to diffuse from the protein's side and hence can reduce the possible formation of protein-additive/solvent hydrogen bonds to protect protein. Following this, the competitive osmoprotective

nature of amino acid molecules may be achieved. However, biological macromolecule, being a complex system requires direct investigation in such solutions to establish the mechanism. Presently, we are working on such aspects in our laboratory.

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